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Research Article

**THE DESIGN OF MODULATION OF REFLEX JOINING THE
TIBIAL MUSCLES TO THE QUADRICEPS AT THE TIME OF
WALK IN HUMANS**¹Dr Abdul Majid Khan, ²Dr Saba Ayesha, ³Dr Sobia Ahmad
¹Nishtar Hospital Multan.**Article Received:** January 2019**Accepted:** February 2019**Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The purpose of this research work was to examine the modulation design of sort latency reflex linking the muscles of the front of tibia bone to the muscles of quadriceps in thigh in normal human being at the time of walking on treadmill.

Methodology: This is quasi empirical research work based on non randomized sampling. This study conducted on ten patients in the Nishtar Hospital Multan and the duration of this study was from September 2017 to August 2018. The response was brought out by the application of stimuli of 3 time's motor threshold in the front muscles on tibia at many moments of walk cycle. Pearson test was in use for the analysis of the collected information for the power of their association.

Results: The reflex displayed an important association with the strength of contraction of muscles of quadriceps particularly at the time of early phase. The association was very weak at the period of transition from posture to swing where femora of rectus displayed a low activity peak. The activity peak in the front tibia was on mean 69 ± 21 meter second preceded than the muscles of quadriceps.

Conclusions: This superiority of activity in front tibialis with the high availability of reflex at the time of initial phase of stance may show a + feed forward impact from the flexor afferents of the ankle to the quadriceps.

Key Words: Superiority, Tibia, Contraction, Excitatory Pathways, Projections, Interneurons.

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INTRODUCTION:

There is promoting proof that group 1 & 2 excitatory pathways are playing very important role management of the human gait. In opposition to the projections of group 1 which are frail and improbable to give reflex support with strength, excitatory pathways of group 2 perform main role in the support and control of the gait [1-3]. It is concluded that the adjustment of EMG during stance & gait in humans are associated to the equilibrium demands of control and projections of group 2 have a main part in the adjustment. There are two fold features of this adjustment;

1. For upright balance control in the limbs of the lower part alters in position of mass centre to the feet [4, 5].
2. For the implementation of the antigravity group muscles activity to secure the joints yielding at the time of stance.

In human beings, stimulation of CPN (common peroneal nerve) is described to suggest quadriceps motoneurons [6] excitation with the initial phase assigned to non monosynaptic group 1 & later stage to afferents in group 2. Interneurons in pathway of reflex are point of convergence for various ascending [7] & descending [6] modifiable pathways. The part of neural pathway in the quadriceps would be much eminent when we think its input to spasticity & firmness in the patients of hemiplegic [8] & parkinsonian [9] respectively. The spread of

excitation of group 2 from receptors of pretibial muscle to the motoneurons of quadriceps is increased after the strike of heel both muscles are in active position [10] or when bending backwards in stance of bipedal [11]. There is not much data about modulation design during the cycle of gait in this subject. The modulation pattern gives more data about the methods participating in the motor control of walk.

METHODOLOGY:

Five males and five females were the part of this study. The study conducted in Nishtar Hospital Multan and the duration of this study was from September 2017 to August 2018. No participant has the previous background of neuromuscular damage or disease. Ethical committee gave the approval of the study. The application of electrical stimuli conducted on peroneal nerve at the time of walk on treadmill. $3 \times MT$ in TA was the set intensity of the provided stimuli. For the compensation of the relative suitable electrodes movement & peroneal nerve, the measurement of MT carried out measured independently at every chosen moment of the cycles of gait. The record of the EMGs of surfaces maintained from TA, VM (vastusmedialis) & RF (rectus femoris) of right leg. Every set of experiment contained three to five minutes consecutive recording of EMG which application of the forty stimuli carried out in the sequences of pseudo randomly.

Two small sized pressure switches under the toe of the feet were in use for the identification of the start

and finish of the gait stance phase. The trigger pulse passed from the DDM (digital delay width module)

for the adjustments of different delays. The research began just after the 5-minute walk on treadmill. Treadmill speed was comfortable and recording of sets carried out. Delays of zero, fifty, one hundred, one hundred and fifty, two hundred, three hundred, five hundred, seven hundred, nine hundred, one thousand and eleven hundred meter second selected. The length of the gait cycle was almost same in all the participants. Stimuli occurred at the same point in the cycle of gait. The recording of the strength of muscles EMG carried out and described as MVC

percentage. Mean RMS was in use for the calculation of the MVC of rectus femoris & vastusmedialis. The association between the reflex magnitude & strength of activity of rectus femoris & vastusmedialis carried out with the assistance of Pearson association coefficient test.

RESULTS:

Rectus femoris & vastusmedialis had the almost same pattern of the activity of EMG as shown in Figure-1.

Figure-1: The pooled intensity of the EMG for VM

The muscles contractions initiate from seventy-five percent & eighty-seven percent of cycle of gait for rectus femoris & vastusmedialis respectively. The zenith of activity for rectus femoris & vastusmedialis occurs after the strike of heel at $4\% \pm 2\%$ of cycle of gait for both muscles. The range of the peak of rectus femoris was thirteen to thirty-nine percent of MVC with a mean value of nineteen percent. The range of VM peak was seventeen to forty percent with an

average of twenty-five percent. The activity of EMG decreased to its lowest amount at average twenty-five percent of gait cycle for rectus vastusmedialis & seventeen percent for rectus femoris.

Reflex was at peak magnitude among the swing of terminal swing & early phase of the stance as shown in Figure-2. It is observable that reflex magnitude catches the peak just after the strike of the heel.

Figure-2: The mean amplitude of the CPQ Reflex in RF and VM during gait cycle

The mean reflexes peak intensity at this period was 77 percent MVC for rectus femoris and one hundred and twenty-one percent MVC for vastusmedialis. A vigorous and plus association was available between the reflex magnitude & strength of the activity of quadriceps in complete gait cycle as shown in Figure-3.

Figure-3: The correlation between the magnitude of the CPQ reflex and the intensity of the background EMG in VM and RF during the whole gait cycle.

DISCUSSION:

The magnitude of the reflex was at its greatest peak

just after the strike of the heel, but at the time of majority of cycles of gait from mid stance to the

swing of terminal reflexes could not be extracted. Fig-3 obviously describes the powerful linear association between the design of the alterations in the magnitude of reflex & strength of activity of EMG activity in rectus femoris & vastusmedialis. The rectus femoris & vastusmedialis muscles activity catches the peak of twenty percent MVC after the strike of the heel. + association among background quadriceps EMG & reflex magnitude at the time of the initial phase of stance may propose an automatic compensation of the gain as elaborated by Matthews [12] in 1986 for the reflex of monosynaptic stretch. The argue was that as the force at background raises so does the rate and number the active motor neurones present to be adjusted by a provided input. It is clear that decreasing inputs have an effect of excitatory on the path [13, 14]. The strong availability of reflex at the time of early phase of stance is constant with that concluded by Marchand Pauvert & Nielsen [10].

Figure-3 describes that majority of the regression line points are present near the 0. The reason is that at the time of largest period of gait, reflex & background EMG are near the values of zero. If the alterations in the activity of background in rectus femoris & vastusmedialis are accountable for modulation of gain of CPQ reflex at the time of gait, it could be supposed that raising the activity of the background EMG during this lengthy inactive period would be the reason of the reappearing of the reflex. This test described that some activity of the EMG at the time of period of transition from stance to phase of swing in rectus femoris as reported by other enquiries [15]. Current tests on man & cat have elaborated that afferent response from extensors of ankle participates in the activation of extensor muscles of ankle in the phase of stance in gait [16, 17]. In case of cat, the mitigation of the phase of stance & the start of the phase of swing are indicated by the reduction in afferent activity by load receptors when in the late phase of stance unloading of extensor muscles carried out [16].

CONCLUSION:

The preference of activity in the front tibialis anterior & vigorous availability of reflex at the time of early phase of stance may show a + feed forward impact from flexor afferents of the ankle to the quadriceps.

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